

**Open Access Patterns, Citation Impact and Co-Authorship Analysis of Amalia Aggeli's
Publications**

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About this Project & Methodology

The selected researcher, Amalia Aggeli, was chosen based on her significant research impact in the field of Biomedical Engineering, as well as her strong academic presence within the Biomedical Engineering Master's program at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. Her work focuses on biomaterials and self-assembling peptide systems, contributing to advancements in biomedical applications and interdisciplinary research. In addition, her extensive publication record and high citation count further support her selection as a representative high-impact researcher for this analysis.

Publication data were retrieved from OpenAlex, a comprehensive open index of scholarly works, and exported in CSV format (Priem et al., 2022). A sample dataset was created by the records containing bibliographic metadata such as publication year, authorship, and citation counts.

The dataset was uploaded to the RAISE platform and assigned a persistent identifier (PID). It was then further analyzed within the RAISE platform using a predefined processing script by Dr. Konstantinidis. Basic preprocessing and handling of missing or inconsistent values were performed implicitly by the analysis script during execution. The experiment execution generated results including statistical summaries, visualizations, and network analysis outputs.

The following research objects were used and cited:

Dataset PID: 10.82136/dataset/08de9c82-96b1-444d-808b-4267755c0045

Script PID (RAISE): 10.82136/script/08de790c-58a3-47dc-8475-cc889e4fe833

Script doi (Zenodo): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19315125>

Experiment PID: 10.82136/381

Results

The analysis provides a comprehensive overview of open access adoption, citation performance, and collaboration patterns within the selected publication dataset ($n = 82$). The figures presented in Appendix A represent the direct outputs of the analysis script, and are referenced here to support a structured interpretation of the results.

The dataset is predominantly composed of closed access publications (69.5%), with open access accounting for 30.5% of the total output (Figure A1). Despite this overall distribution, a strong temporal shift toward open access publishing is observed. Specifically, the temporal distribution of publications (Figure A2) and the open access rate trend (Figure A5) reveal a marked increase in open access adoption after 2015, with rates exceeding 80% in recent years. This transition suggests a strategic or systemic change in publishing practices rather than gradual evolution.

Citation performance across access types shows minimal differences. Open access publications exhibit an average of 72.76 citations, compared to 72.53 for closed access publications (Figure A3). Yearly citation patterns (Figure A3) indicate substantial variability, with no consistent advantage for either access type across time. These findings are reinforced by statistical testing (Mann–Whitney U test, $p = 0.1081$), indicating that the observed differences are not statistically significant.

Further breakdown of open access categories (Figure A1) shows that gold open access constitutes the largest proportion among OA types, followed by hybrid and green models. Collaboration appears to play a more decisive role in open access adoption. As shown in Figure A6, publications with larger numbers of co-authors exhibit higher open access rates, with papers

involving 12 or more authors reaching full open access representation. This finding aligns with established research showing that scientific collaboration networks play a central role in shaping research productivity and knowledge dissemination (Newman, 2001).

The co-authorship network reveals a dense and centralized collaboration structure (Figures A7 and A8), comprising 181 unique collaborators with an average of 6.6 authors per publication. The central node, representing the selected researcher, is strongly connected to a core group of frequent collaborators. The top collaborators (Figure A4) highlight N. Boden as the most prominent contributor, participating in 37 publications. The network visualization colored by open access rate (Figure A7) indicates that certain collaboration clusters are associated with higher open access activity, while others remain predominantly closed. When examining the network through citation impact (Figure A8), influential collaborators are not always aligned with open access-heavy groups. This divergence suggests that citation performance is driven more by research impact and collaboration history than by access model alone.

Discussion

The results point to a clear structural shift in publishing behavior rather than isolated trends. The rapid transition toward open access after 2015 suggests alignment with broader policy and funding changes in biomedical research, indicating that the selected researcher is responsive to evolving norms in scientific dissemination rather than acting independently of them.

At the same time, the absence of a measurable citation advantage for open access publications contrasts with prior large-scale studies that report a modest citation benefit for open access outputs (Piwowar et al., 2018). Instead, citation performance could be that it is influenced

more by the researcher's position within an established collaboration network and the consistency of research output (Bornmann & Daniel, 2008).

The co-authorship analysis highlights a highly centralized yet stable collaboration structure, where a core group of recurring collaborators plays a key role in sustaining productivity. This pattern is typical of mature research profiles and suggests that the selected researcher operates within a well-established scientific network rather than forming transient collaborations.

An important observation is that larger teams appear more likely to publish openly, which may reflect shared resources, coordinated dissemination strategies, or compliance with funding requirements. This indicates that open access behavior is not purely an individual choice but is shaped by the structure and scale of collaborative research.

Finally, the divergence between citation impact and open access patterns within the collaboration network suggests that these dimensions function independently. High-impact collaborators are not necessarily those associated with higher open access rates.

In conclusion, these results demonstrate that open access adoption, citation performance, and collaboration dynamics are interconnected but not directly dependent on one another. Moreover, it can be argued that collaboration structure and research continuity appear to play a more decisive role in shaping scholarly influence. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of considering both social and systemic factors when evaluating research practices, particularly in highly collaborative fields such as biomedical engineering.

Appendix A: Supplementary Figures

**Open Access Status Distribution
(n=82 publications)**

Figure A1. Open Access Status Distribution of Publications (n = 82)

Figure A2. Temporal Distribution of Open Access vs Closed Access Publications

Figure A3. Average Citations per Paper by Year and Access Type

Figure A4. Top Collaborators by Number of Joint Publications and Open Access Rate

Figure A5. Open Access Rate Trend Over Time

Figure A6. Open Access Rate by Number of Co-authors

Co-Authorship Network
Edge Color: OA Rate | Edge Width: Collaboration Count | Node Size: Total Collaborations

Figure A7. Co-authorship Network Colored by Open Access Rate

Co-Authorship Network
Node Color: Avg Citations | Edge Color: Collaboration Count | Node Size: Total Collaborations

Figure A8. Co-authorship Network Colored by Average Citation Impact

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